

Assessment of Phoria in young adults in a district Mullana Haryana, India

Rozy kumari¹ Razia Bano* Nitesh Pradhan³

Assistant professor, Vivekanand Global University Jaipur Rajasthan

Assistant professor, Era University Lucknow India

Assistant professor, Maharishi Markandeswar University India

Corresponding Author

Razia Bano

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ABSTRACT

Background: The heterophoria is an important indicator of binocular function. The relationship between the near and far phoria measures has historically been a critical finding in the diagnosis of convergence and divergence anomalies. Asthenopic symptoms such as pain, blurred vision, headache, and diplopia can be caused by phorias. Corrective lenses may be used to treat Phorias. These may or may not include the use of

prisms and eye exercises such as the pen push-up test, which should be done three times per day, as well as vision therapy.

Aims: To determine the types of phorias in various degrees in all refractive error patients of various ages (5-45).

Study Design: Cross sectional Study

Method: Patients visited MMIMSR Ophthalmology OPD (Out Patient Department) for an eye exam. Which patients (5-45 years old) were asked for a specific history of trauma, eye surgery, infection, or allergy? Those patients with such a history were excluded, and the rest of the symptomatic and asymptomatic cases of headache, near work problem meeting the criteria forming the study sample were informed about Orthoptics workup and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Result: Study was conducted on 100 patients between the age group of 5-45 years, in the Department of Ophthalmology of Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Science and Research, Ambala. In our study, we found a prevalence of Exophoria at distance is (7%) and at near Exophoria (10%), Esophoria(2%) among youth (5-45) age group.

Conclusion: In our study, we found a prevalence of Exophoria at distance is (7%) and at near Exophoria (10%), Esophoria(2%) among youth (5-45) age group.

Keywords: Exophoria, Esophoria, Phoria , Prism bar cover test, Cover test.

INTRODUCTION

BINOCULAR SINGLE VISION:

This condition of simultaneous vision is made possible by the proper coordination of the two eyes, which enables the slightly different images that are produced in each eye to be perceived as a single image through the process of fusion. Therefore, binocular single vision is the combination of two eyes' vision into a single percept. The state of simultaneous vision with two seeing eyes (neither of which need necessarily be normal) that happens when a person fixes his or her visual attention on an object of regard is known as binocular single vision, according to Romano and Romano.

GRADES OF BINOCULAR SINGLE VISION:

- (A) Simultaneous perception
- (B) Fusion
- (C) Stereopsis

ANOMALIES OF BINOCULAR SINGLE VISION: Anomalies in binocular single vision occur when a manifest deviation or heterophoria (which may be Esophoria, Exophoria Hyperphoria, Hypophoria, Cyclophoria, or a combination of these) is present while a person views a target binocularly with no occlusion of either eye.

The individual is unable to align the gaze of each eye in order to achieve fusion. When the NRC (Normal retinal correspondence) is interrupted, the corresponding retinal elements are no longer directed at the same object.²

THESE RESULTS IN:

- (1) CONFUSION
- (2) DIPLOPIA
- (3) SUPPRESSION
- (4) AMBLYOPIA

(1) CONFUSION: Is similar to diplopia; it is associated with ocular misalignment, when correlating retinal areas are stimulated by dissimilar stimuli, resulting in the appearance of two different objects at the same location in the field. Because the eyes are misaligned, dissimilar images fall on each corresponding fovea, causing confusion rather than diplopia in some patients.

(2) DIPLOPIA: An object point is localised in two different subjective visual directions when it stimulates non-corresponding or disparate retinal elements at the same time. An object point seen in two directions at the same time appears double. Double vision is a symptom of retinal disparity.³

(3) SUPPRESSION: It is a sensory adaptation to squinting in which only one eye works, which can be unilateral or alternating.⁴

IT CAN BE OF TWO TYPES –

- (a) Facultative suppression
- (b) Obligatory suppression

(4) AMBLYOPIA - A condition characterised by unilateral or bilateral decreases in visual functions as a result of formed vision deprivation and/or abnormal binocular interaction that cannot be explained by an ocular media or visual pathway disorder (is recognised as lazy eye). In appropriate cases, treatment interventions can reverse it.

CLASSIFICATION OF AMBLYOPIA:

- (a) Strabismic amblyopia
- (b) Stimulus deprivation
- (c) Anisometropic amblyopia
- (d) Meridional amblyopia

MANAGEMENT/TREATMENT OF AMBLYOPIA:

Early detection of amblyopia is critical for proper management because it makes it easier to treat the patient and provide appropriate treatment, potentially resulting in vision recovery or improvement. The following steps are involved in the treatment of amblyopia:

Prevention: Vision screening program beginning at birth are the most effective way to diagnose and treat amblyopia.

Treatment: To begin treating amblyopia, we must first identify the source of the vision loss and attempt to eliminate it, such as congenital cataract, congenital ptosis, corneal opacity, and so on. Then, before beginning occlusion therapy, we should try to balance the vision of both eyes using the trial and error method of refraction. Following that, we will attempt to correct the ocular dominance by locating the dominant eye; to accomplish this, we will use occlusion therapy, penalization, active stimulation, pleoptics, and pharmacological manipulation.

- (1) Occlusion therapy: In this case, we must occlude the dominant eye with a patch on the skin, gauze pad and tape, Doyne's rubber occlude, opaque contact lens, and so on. The normal eye will be covered with a patch, and the amblyopic eye will have to work. The patient will be asked to do exercises like joining dots, thread beading, and so on, and the brain will send information to this eye, which will help to restore vision in the amblyopic eye.

- (2) Penalisation: It is a method of forcing the amblyopic eye to work harder by penalising the healthy eye with glasses and a cycloplegic drug. This method is as effective as patching. Two methods of punishment are used. Atropine penalization (in which the normal eye is atropined and the amblyopic eye is overcorrected with +2 or +3 dioptré) and optical penalization (in which the normal eye is atropined and the amblyopic eye is overcorrected with +2 or +3 dioptré (in this we will prescribe more plus lens to the sound eye and force the amblyopic eye to use).
- (3) Active stimulation therapy: After occluding the sound eye, a 7-minute stimulation with a slowly rotating high contrast square wave ring of different spatial frequencies is performed once a week.

PHORIA: A phoria is a misalignment of the eyes that occurs when binocular vision is obstructed and the two eyes are no longer looking at the same object. The misalignment of the eyes occurs when a person is tired, so it is not constant. The cover/uncover test is used to identify phoria.

Heterophoria:- It is a condition in which the extraocular muscle balance is imperfect due to intrinsic weakness in one or more of the extraocular muscles, and the eye has a tendency to deviate from its normal position as soon as the corrective fusion reflex is withdrawn by dissociating binocular vision.

Types of heterophoria:-

- (1) Esophoria:-It is the eye's predisposition for inward deviation of the eyeball, which is nasally.
- (2) Exophoria:-It is the temporal tendency of the eye for the deviation of the eyeball outwards.
- (3) Hyperphoria:- It is the eye's predisposition for upward deviation of the eyeball.
- (4) Hypophoria:- It is the eye's predisposition for downward eyeball deviation.
- (5) Cyclophoria:- It is the eye's predisposition to rotate the eyeball around the fixation axis.¹⁰

Treatment of heterophoria:

Treatment of heterophoria includes:

- (1) Optical correction (2) Orthoptic exercise (3)prismotherapy (4)Miotics
 - (5)Surgery
- (1) Optical treatment: Exophoria occurs when both eyes are undercorrected by an equal amount of spherical plus power, causing the patient to constantly accommodate and, as a result, induces accommodative convergence. In the case of esophoria, the patient should have as much spherical plus power correction as is compatible with his

or her best visual acuity. In hyperphoria, the prismatic effect of the lens should be removed to help relieve the patient's eye stress. An effort should be made to correct the astigmatic refractive error in cyclophoria.

- (2) Orthoptic treatment:-The goal of esophoria is to improve the amplitude of fusional divergence; this will be accomplished through divergence exercises with prisms, synoptophore divergence exercises, diploscope, stereogram, and Remy separator exercises. The goal of exophoria is to improve fusional convergence through convergence exercises with prisms, synoptophores, stereogram charts, and pen pushups.
- (3) Prismotherapy:- Prisms can be used as an orthoptic exercise training device. The prism's role in horizontal phoria correction is permanent.
- (4) Miotic drugs: Because of the high AC/A ratio, this is the treatment of choice in near esophoria. Miotics facilitate accommodation so that less than normal innervations are required to obtain a given accommodative response.
- (5) Surgery in horizontal phorias, surgery becomes necessary if the symptoms are not relieved by

exercises. If the vertical phoria is too large to be treated with a prism, surgery is required.¹²

PHORIA AMONG YOUNGESTS:-

IN CHILDREN:-Chen et al. and Lam. found a high prevalence of orthophoria (no misalignment) in children under the age of six using the subjective Maddox wing and the alternating cover test, respectively. Babinsky et al. were using objective testing and a longer period of dissociation to demonstrate adult-like exophorias in young children at 33 cm. We recently confirmed, using similar objective eye tracking techniques, that even three to five month old infants showed small exophoria at an 80 cm viewing distance, similar to preschool children and adults.

IN ADULTS:-The mean distance phoria in adults ranges from 0 to 1 prism dioptre (pd) exophoria (SD around 2 pd) for a target at a viewing distance of 6 m or 20 ft, while the mean near phoria for a target at 33 or 40 cm is typically exophoric and ranges between 3 and 6 pd. Phoria has also been well defined in older school-aged children (>six years), with mean values ranging from 1 pd esophoria to 1 pd exophoria at distance and orthophoria to 3 pd exophoria at close.

OLDER PATIENTS: In elderly patients, poorly controlled phorias are frequently associated with asthenopic symptoms such as blurred vision, eyestrain, headache, and decreased stereopsis. They may also be linked to non-strabismic binocular vision issues, such as convergence

insufficiency or excess, which can affect academic performance in school-aged children.¹²

AIMS

To find out the prevalence of Phoria at distance and near among age between 5 - 45 year old.

OBJECTIVES

To find out the prevalence of Phoria at Distance in age 5 - 45 year.

To find out the prevalence of Phoria at Near in age 5 - 45 year.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

MATERIALS

STUDY DESIGN: Cross-sectional study

STUDY AREA: The research was carried out at the Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Science and Research, Mullana, Ambala, in the Department of Ophthalmology (Haryana).

STUDY POPULATION: Patients who attended the Ophthalmology Outpatient Department (OPD) at the Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Science and Research, Mullana, Ambala (Haryana) during the study periods and met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were chosen.

SELECTION CRITERIA OF PATIENTS:

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- *Age between 5 to 45 years.
- *Patients those who have Asthenopic symptoms
- *Patients are prepared to provide informed consent.
- *There was no prior history of any ocular pathology.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- *Less than 5 years and more than 45 years
- *Amblyopia, Tropia, ocular disease such as glaucoma corneal opacity, cataract, pregnant lady, choronic obstructive pulmonary disease, diabetes mellitus.
- *Patients unable to provide informed consent.

METHODS - SCREENING

PROCEDURES:

- (1) History
- (2) General and systemic examination
- (3) Best corrected visual acuity according to snellens chart for distance and near vision which was

converted to Log MAR Scale using Standard table.

This comparative cross-sectional

study included 100 patients in total. The phorias of all refractive error patients were assessed before and after refractive correction. Patients range in age from five to forty-five years. The data came from the Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Hospital. Phoria was detected in selected subjects using the following equipment/tests: before and after BCVA (Best corrected visual acuity),

cover/uncover test (for distance and near), prism bar cover test (PBCT) for near and distance.

COVER TEST (FOR DISTANCE):-

The purpose of the cover test is to determine the presence and type of heterophoria (latent eye deviation) at a distance.

COVER TEST (FOR NEAR): The purpose of the cover test is to determine the presence of heterophoria (latent deviation of the eye) at near range.

PRISM BAR COVER TEST(PBCT): The prism cover test must be carried out at three distinct distances (33 cm, 6m, and greater than 6 metres). Before beginning the test, make sure the patient is sitting up straight with their chin and head straight. Patients with a head tilt are always tested with and without their head tilt. The cover test results will tell you what

type of deviation you have and how you

PREVALENCE OF PHORIA AT NEAR

should hold your prism for the next stage of the test. BASE OUT for an esodeviation (eye turned in), IN for an exodeviation (eye turned out), UP for a hypodeviation (eye turned down), and DOWN for a hyperdeviation (eye turned up)

Fig. PBCT horizontal & vertical

Fig. PBCT for distance

PREVALENCE OF PHORIA AT DISTANCE

Result:

Study was conducted on 100 patients between the age group of 5-45 years, in the Department of Ophthalmology of Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Science and Research, Mullana, Ambala.

Figure. showed Prevalence of Phoria at Distance

PHORIA AT DISTANCE				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
ORTHOPHORIA	93	93	93	93.0
EXOPHORIA	7	7	7	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

In our study, we found a prevalence of Exophoria at Distance (7%) among youth (5-45) age group.

Figure. showed Prevalence of Phoria at Near

PHORIA AT NEAR				
PHORIA	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
ORTHOPHORIA	88	88.0	88.0	88.0
EXOPHORIA	10	10.0	10.0	98.0
ESOPHORIA	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

In our study, we found a prevalence of Exophoria at Near (10%) and Esophoria (2%) among youth (5-45) age group.

CONCLUSION

Study was conducted on 100 patients between the age group of 5-45 years, PBCT has been done vertically and horizontally, Cover – Uncover performed to assess heterophoria.

In our study, we found a prevalence of Exophoria at distance (7%) among youth (5-45) age group.

Also, we found a prevalence of Exophoria at near (10%) and Esophoria (2%) among youth (5-45) age group.

LIMITATIONS

Sample size was too small, we excluded individuals who had Refractive Error in association of phorias.

REFERENCES:

1. KHURANA, A., 2018. *Theory and practice of squint and orthoptics*. Binocular vision. Heterophoria. Evaluation of a

- case of strabismus and orthoptic instruments. [Place of publication not identified]: CBS.57-58,81,213-216,102-103p.
2. Eophtha.com. 2022. *Binocular Single Vision And Its Anomalies..* [online] Available at: <<https://www.eophtha.com/posts/binocular-single-vision-and-its-anomalies>> [Accessed 17 June 2022].
 3. Webeye.opth.uiowa.edu. 2022. *EyeRounds.org: Tutorial: Binocular Vision*. Diplopia[online] Available at: <<https://webeye.opth.uiowa.edu/eyeforum/tutorials/bhola-binocularvision.htm>> [Accessed 17 June 2022].
 4. Sharma, P., 2013. *Starbismus simplified*. 2nd ed. Examination of a case of squint. The physiology og binocular vision, Amblyopia and anomalous retinal correspondence. New Delhi, India: CBS Publishers & Distributors.84,42p
 5. Rohatgi, J., 2003. *Squint*. Sensory adaptation in concomitant squint. New Delhi, India: CBS Publishers.70p
 6. Slideshare.net. 2022. *Amblyopia*. classification and treatment. [online] Available at: <https://www.slideshare.net/Nedhina/a>
 7. Schwartz, S., n.d. *Visual perception A clinical orientation*. 5th ed. Development and maturation of vision. York: McGraw-Hill education.341-342,346p.
 8. American Academy of Ophthalmology. 2022. *Amblyopia: Types, Diagnosis, Treatment, and New Perspectives*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.aao.org/disease-review/amblyopia-types-diagnosis-treatment-new-perspectiv>>Table-2[Accessed 17 June 2022].
 9. Verywell Health. 2022. *Eye Movement Disorders of the Eyes*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.verywellhealth.com/phorias-and-tropias-3421552#:~:text=Understanding%20Phorias,present%20all%20of%20the%20time.>>> [Accessed 17 June 2022].
 10. SINHA, P., 2022. *TREATMENT OF HETEROPHORIA - Optography*. [online] Optography. Available at: <https://optography.org/treatment-of-heterophoria/> Figure 5.>[Accessed 18 June 2022].

11. Troyer ME, Sreenivasan V, Peper TJ, Candy TR. The heterophoria of 3-5 year old children as a function of viewing distance and target type. *Ophthalmic Physiol Opt.* 2017 Jan;37(1):7-15. doi: 10.1111/opo.12342. Epub 2016 Dec 5. PMID: 27921322; PMCID: PMC5195916.
12. Chung KM, Chong E. Near esophoria is associated with high myopia. *Clin Exp Optom.* 2000 Mar-Apr;83(2):71-75. doi: 10.1111/j.1444-0938.2000.tb04895.x. PMID: 12472457.
13. Hashemi H, Pakzad R, Nabovati P, Azad Shahraki F, Ostadimoghaddam H, Aghamirsalim M, Pakbin M, Yekta A, Khoshhal F, Khabazkhoob M. The prevalence of tropia, phoria and their types in a student population in Iran. *Strabismus.* 2020 Mar;28(1):35-41. doi: 10.1080/09273972.2019.1697300. Epub 2019 Dec 23. PMID: 31868064.
14. Tannen B, Good K, Ciuffreda KJ, Moore KJ. Prevalence of esophoria in concussed patients. *J Optom.* 2019 Jan-Mar;12(1):64-68. doi: 10.1016/j.optom.2018.02.003. Epub 2018 Mar 27. PMID: 29602686; PMCID: PMC6318546.
15. Hashemi H, Yekta A, Jafarzadehpur E, Ostadimoghaddam H, Eshrati B, Mohazzab-Torabi S, Khabazkhoob M, Soroush S. The prevalence of strabismus in 7- year-old schoolchildren in Iran. *Strabismus.* 2015;23(1):1-7. doi: 10.3109/09273972.2014.999795. Epub 2015 Jan 13. PMID: 25584828.
16. Qian X, Liu B, Wang J, Wei N, Qi X, Li X, Li J, Zhang Y, Hua N, Ning Y, Ding G, Ma X, Wang B. Prevalence of refractive errors in Tibetan adolescents. *BMC Ophthalmol.* 2018 May 11;18(1):118. doi: 10.1186/s12886-018-0780-8. PMID: 29747615; PMCID: PMC5946460.
17. Maqbool J, Amir A, Iftikhar A. Assessment of types of phorias in myopic patients before and after refractive correction. *Adv Ophthalmol Vis Syst.* 2021;11(2):37-42.